

GREEN MARKETING PRACTICES AND CUSTOMER LOYALTY OF THE HOSPITALITY SECTOR IN YENAGOA, BAYELSA STATE

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Abstract: *The study investigated the relationship between green marketing practices and customer loyalty in the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria, using Customer Value Theory as the theoretical foundation. The study was anchored on a positivist research philosophy and adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. The population of the study was considered infinite, and a sample size of 384 respondents was determined using Cochran's formula. Data was collected primarily through a structured questionnaire, which was validated through content and face validity procedures. The reliability of the research instrument was confirmed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. A total of 384 questionnaires were administered, of which 212 were correctly completed and returned, representing a valid response rate used for analysis. The data were analysed using univariate, bivariate, and multivariate statistical techniques to examine the link among the study variables. The empirical findings revealed that green products, green price, green promotion, green distribution, and green branding each have a positive and statistically significant relationship with customer repurchase intentions in the hospitality industry. These results indicate that environmentally responsible marketing practices significantly enhance customers' perceived value and increase their likelihood of repeat patronage. The study concludes that green marketing mix strategies are critical determinants of customer repurchase behaviour in the hospitality industry. Based on the Customer Value Theory, the findings suggest that customers derive higher value from environmentally sustainable offerings, which in turn influences their behavioural intentions. The study recommends amongst others that hospitality firms in Yenagoa integrate comprehensive green marketing strategies to enhance customer retention, strengthen brand loyalty, and achieve sustainable competitive advantage.*

Introduction

The growing global concern for environmental sustainability has significantly transformed business operations across industries, including the hospitality sector. Organizations are increasingly adopting environmentally friendly business practices to meet stakeholder expectations, enhance corporate image, and achieve competitive advantage. Hotels and other hospitality establishments are increasingly adopting environmentally responsible practices not only to comply with environmental regulations but also to attract environmentally conscious consumers. Green marketing has emerged as a strategic business approach through which organizations communicate their environmental commitments and sustainable business practices to customers (Andniran et al, 2026). In the hospitality sector, green marketing encompasses activities such as energy conservation, waste reduction, water management, eco-friendly product usage, sustainable sourcing, environmental certification, and the promotion of environmentally responsible consumption among guests. These practices have become important determinants of customer perceptions, satisfaction, and loyalty. According to Seo et al (2024), one strategic approach that has gained considerable attention is green marketing, which involves designing, promoting, and delivering products and services in ways that minimize environmental harm while satisfying customer needs.

Green marketing has evolved from a peripheral business activity into a core strategic function. It encompasses environmentally responsible practices such as waste reduction, energy conservation, recycling programs, sustainable sourcing, eco-friendly product offerings, and environmental communication initiatives. In the hospitality industry, these practices are increasingly integrated into hotel operations and marketing strategies as organizations seek to attract environmentally conscious consumers (Chang et al., 2024). According to contemporary marketing literature, green marketing involves the planning, implementation, and control of products, pricing, promotion, and distribution in a manner that minimizes negative environmental impacts while satisfying consumer needs. As environmental awareness continues to increase globally, customers increasingly evaluate businesses based on their environmental performance and sustainability commitments. Consequently, organizations that effectively communicate and implement green initiatives are more likely to develop stronger relationships with customers and gain a competitive advantage (Aly, 2023)

The hospitality industry is particularly relevant in discussions of environmental sustainability because hotels consume significant quantities of water, energy, and other natural resources while generating substantial waste. Consequently, many hotels have adopted green initiatives such as water conservation systems, renewable energy technologies, eco-friendly building designs, waste management programs, and

sustainable procurement policies. These initiatives not only contribute to environmental protection but also influence customer perceptions and purchasing decisions (Uludag et al., 2024). Within the hospitality industry, environmental sustainability has become a critical strategic issue because hotels consume substantial amounts of energy, water, and other natural resources while generating considerable waste. As a result, hospitality operators worldwide have adopted green initiatives such as renewable energy systems, towel and linen reuse programs, waste recycling, eco-friendly building designs, and sustainable procurement practices. These initiatives are often integrated into marketing communications to enhance corporate image and influence customer behavior. Studies have demonstrated that customers increasingly prefer hotels that exhibit genuine environmental responsibility, particularly among younger and environmentally conscious market segments (Kumar et al, 2025).

Customer loyalty remains a critical determinant of organizational success in the hospitality sector. Customer loyalty refers to a customer's willingness to continue patronizing a service provider, recommend the organization to others, and maintain a positive attitude toward the brand despite competitive alternatives. Loyal customers contribute to increased profitability through repeat patronage, positive word-of-mouth communication, and reduced customer acquisition costs (Dedat & Rodrigues, 2025). Customer loyalty remains one of the most important outcomes sought by hospitality organizations. Loyalty refers to a customer's

commitment to repeatedly patronize a service provider, recommend it to others, and maintain a positive attitude toward the organization despite competitive alternatives. In the hospitality sector, loyal customers contribute significantly to profitability through repeat visits, positive word-of-mouth communication, reduced marketing costs, and enhanced brand reputation. Researchers increasingly argue that customer loyalty is influenced not only by service quality and customer satisfaction but also by customers' perceptions of a firm's social and environmental responsibility (Mohammadi et al, 2023).

Recent studies indicate that green marketing practices have a positive influence on customer loyalty. Customers increasingly prefer organizations that demonstrate environmental responsibility and sustainability commitment. Research has shown that green marketing initiatives enhance customer satisfaction, trust, perceived value, and corporate image, which subsequently strengthen customer loyalty (Po & Jiang, 2023). Similarly, Chang et al. (2024) found that customers who perceive hotel environmental practices positively are more likely to exhibit repeat purchase intentions and long-term loyalty behaviors. Several theoretical perspectives support the relationship between green marketing practices and customer loyalty. Stakeholder Theory suggests that organizations that address stakeholder concerns, including environmental sustainability, are more likely to receive stakeholder support and commitment. Relationship Marketing Theory argues that trust, commitment, and customer satisfaction are essential components of long-term customer

relationships. Social Exchange Theory further explains that customers tend to reciprocate socially responsible organizational behavior through favorable attitudes and loyalty behaviors (Uludag et al., 2024; Salem et al., 2026).

In developing countries such as Nigeria, environmental sustainability is becoming increasingly important due to growing concerns about pollution, waste management, climate change, and environmental degradation. Although the adoption of green marketing practices remains relatively low compared to developed economies, many hospitality organizations are beginning to recognize the strategic importance of environmental responsibility in attracting and retaining customers (Adeniran et al., 2026). Yenagoa, the capital city of Bayelsa State, presents a unique setting for investigating the relationship between green marketing practices and customer loyalty. Situated within the Niger Delta region, Yenagoa faces significant environmental challenges arising from oil exploration activities, environmental pollution, and ecological degradation. These environmental concerns have heightened public awareness of sustainability issues and may influence customer attitudes toward environmentally responsible hospitality businesses. The hospitality industry in Yenagoa has experienced considerable growth due to increasing commercial activities, government functions, tourism development, and urbanization. As competition among hotels intensifies, operators are seeking innovative strategies to differentiate themselves and build

lasting customer relationships. Green marketing practices may serve as an effective tool for enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty while simultaneously promoting environmental sustainability. However, empirical evidence regarding the effectiveness of green marketing practices in influencing customer loyalty within the hospitality sector of Yenagoa remains limited. Furthermore, most existing studies on green marketing and customer loyalty have been conducted in developed countries and major urban centers, leaving a significant research gap in emerging hospitality markets such as Yenagoa. Cultural, economic, and environmental differences may affect how customers perceive and respond to green marketing initiatives.

Against this backdrop, this study seeks to examine the relationship between green marketing practices and customer loyalty in the hospitality sector of Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study intends to assess how various dimensions of green marketing practices, including green products, green promotion, green pricing, and green operational practices—influence customer loyalty outcomes such as repeat patronage, positive word-of-mouth communication, customer commitment, and advocacy. The findings will contribute to both academic literature and managerial practice by providing empirical evidence on the role of sustainability-oriented marketing strategies in enhancing customer loyalty within the hospitality sector. Therefore, there is a need for context-specific research to investigate the relationship between green marketing practices

and customer loyalty in the hospitality sector of Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

Problem of the Study

The hospitality industry is increasingly operating in an environment where environmental sustainability has become a critical determinant of organizational competitiveness and customer preference. Growing concerns about climate change, environmental degradation, resource depletion, and waste generation have compelled businesses to adopt sustainable practices and communicate their environmental commitments through green marketing initiatives. Within the hospitality sector, green marketing practices such as energy conservation, waste reduction, eco-friendly product usage, water management, and sustainable promotional activities have gained prominence as strategic tools for enhancing organizational image and attracting environmentally conscious customers (Seo et al., 2024).

Despite the growing adoption of green marketing practices globally, the effectiveness of these initiatives in generating customer loyalty remains a subject of ongoing scholarly debate. While several studies have reported positive relationships between green marketing practices and customer loyalty through mechanisms such as customer satisfaction, trust, and perceived value (Chang et al., 2024; Salem et al., 2026), other studies suggest that customers may not always translate favorable environmental perceptions into actual loyalty behaviors, particularly in developing economies where purchasing decisions are often influenced

by economic considerations, service quality, and price sensitivity (Dedat & Rodrigues, 2025). This inconsistency in empirical findings indicates the need for further investigation into the contextual factors influencing the green marketing–customer loyalty relationship.

In the hospitality sector, customer loyalty is particularly important because it contributes to repeat patronage, positive word-of-mouth communication, customer retention, and long-term profitability. However, increasing competition among hotels has made customer loyalty more difficult to achieve and sustain. Consequently, hospitality managers are seeking innovative strategies to differentiate their services and strengthen customer relationships. Green marketing has emerged as one such strategy, yet there is insufficient empirical evidence regarding the extent to which environmentally responsible marketing practices influence customer loyalty in many developing-country contexts, including Nigeria (Turan et al., 2024).

The Nigerian hospitality industry has witnessed significant growth over the past decade, accompanied by increasing awareness of environmental sustainability issues. Nevertheless, the adoption and implementation of green marketing practices among hospitality establishments remain relatively uneven. Many hotels continue to focus primarily on traditional marketing approaches without fully integrating sustainability considerations into their operational and promotional strategies. Furthermore, empirical studies examining the relationship between green marketing practices and customer loyalty within the Nigerian

hospitality sector remain limited, with most existing studies concentrating on developed economies and selected Asian markets (Chang et al., 2024; Seo et al., 2024). The situation is even more pronounced in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, where environmental concerns are particularly significant due to the region's exposure to oil exploration activities, pollution, environmental degradation, and ecological challenges associated with the Niger Delta. These environmental realities have heightened public awareness of sustainability issues and may influence customer expectations regarding corporate environmental responsibility. However, despite the environmental sensitivity of the region, little is known about whether hospitality customers in Yenagoa consider green marketing practices when making patronage decisions or whether such practices influence their loyalty toward hospitality establishments. Moreover, previous studies have largely focused on broad sustainability concepts without adequately examining the specific dimensions of green marketing practices—such as green product offerings, green pricing, green promotion, and green operational practices—and how these dimensions individually or collectively influence customer loyalty outcomes. This gap limits the ability of hospitality managers to identify the most effective sustainability strategies for enhancing customer retention and competitive advantage (Salem et al., 2026).

Another important concern is the contextual limitation of existing literature. Most empirical studies on green marketing and customer loyalty have been conducted in developed

countries where environmental awareness, regulatory frameworks, and consumer purchasing power differ considerably from those of developing economies. Consequently, findings from these studies may not be directly applicable to the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, where socio-economic, cultural, and environmental factors may shape customer perceptions and behaviors differently (Dedat & Rodrigues, 2025). Therefore, the problem confronting this study is the lack of sufficient empirical evidence regarding the relationship between green marketing practices and customer loyalty within the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. Specifically, it remains unclear whether the adoption of green marketing practices by hospitality establishments significantly influences customer loyalty and which dimensions of green marketing contribute most effectively to customer retention. Addressing this knowledge gap is necessary for advancing theoretical understanding, informing managerial decision-making, and supporting the development of sustainable hospitality practices within the Niger Delta region and Nigeria as a whole.

Research Objective

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of green marketing practices on customer loyalty of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. The following are the specific objectives:

1. To examine how green product attributes influence customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.
2. To evaluate whether the perceived value of green-priced products contributes to higher

customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

3. To assess how green promotional messages and environmental claims enhance customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

4. To determine the effects of green distribution practices and customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

5. To investigate the influence of green brand identity on customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were analysed in this study:

RQ1: How do green product attributes influence customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

RQ2: How does customers' perception of green pricing affect their customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

RQ3: What is the effect of green promotional activities on customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

RQ4: How do green distribution practices impact customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

RQ5: How does green branding identity influence customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in this study:

HO₁: Green products attribute does not have a positive and statistically significant effect on customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

HO₂: Perceived fairness of green pricing does not have a positive and statistically significant impact on customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

HO₃: Green promotional activities do not have a positive and statistically significant effect on customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

HO₄: Green distribution practices do not a positive and statistically significant influence customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

HO₅: Green branding do not have a positive and statistically significant effect on customer repurchase intention of the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

**Literature Review
Conceptual Framework**

Conceptual Framework: Author's Design (2025)

Concept of Green Marketing: The term "green marketing" can be defined by recognizing and fulfilling the needs of customers who are environmentally conscious. Secondly, the conventional method to marketing but with an emphasis on environmentally friendly options (Gustavo et al., 2021). Thirdly, the integration of green marketing with additional firm procedures in both the upstream and downstream supply chains (Nath & Siepong, 2022; Giantari &

Sukaatmadja, 2021). Green marketing is a promotional strategy that shows the positive effects of goods or services on the surrounding environment by employing a diversity of marketing channels (Alkhatib et al, 2023). It is an integrated marketing approach whereby firms design, produce, package, distribute and promote goods and services in environmentally responsible ways with the goal of satisfying human needs and wants, while minimizing negative effects on the natural ecosystem

supporting sustainability, and creating social and corporate value (Badhwar et al, 2024; Bhardwaj et al, 2023). According to Giwa-Amu (2022), green marketing is one technique of persuading consumer purchasing behavior, and it significantly influences consumers to buy ecologically friendly products. Furthermore, it brings customer attention to the benefits of their purchasing habits, both for themselves and the environment. It is also described as a strategy used for increasing the value of goods or services using sustainability claims about characteristics or systems, business practices that add value in three different ways, management practices, and the creation of environmentally friendly products or services (Giantari & Sukaatmadja, 2021). Green marketing is defined as ecologically beneficial marketing efforts with the aim of generating money by offering exchanges that fulfill a business's social and economic performance goals. Researchers and marketing experts share a common concern and keen interest in how to effectively and efficiently carry out green marketing strategies for sustainable consumption. In a diverse opinion Alamsyah et al. (2020) examines green marketing from a promotional perspective which comprised green advertising, green brand image, green awareness and green purchase intentions. This view is an all-inclusive nature of green marketing where everything an organisation does to market its products should embed green marketing concepts. According to Kisieliauskas and Jančaitis, (2022), green marketing entails promoting efforts to be environmentally friendly to a target audience. It endeavours to

build an environmentally sensitive image and not only about promoting an offering with environmental attributes, going green also requires brands to change their message and production process. Sustainable marketing, on the other hand, takes the notion of “green” to a deeper level. It involves creating awareness for a better and more sustainable future. Sustainability addresses environmental degradation, climate change, inequality, poverty, peace and justice to achieve harmony between nature and humans. By adopting green marketing practices, companies aim to reduce their environmental impact, enhance their corporate image, and cater to the needs of the green consumer segment. One key aspect of green marketing involves understanding how it influences consumers repurchase intention toward environmentally friendly products and services (Tien et al, 2020). The concept of green marketing provides several benefits ranging from as a viable strategy for reducing energy use and promoting environmentally friendly behaviour and improvements to the design of goods, manufacturing material choices, packaging, advertisements, advertising tools, and other green marketing initiatives that reflect both the needs of consumers and sustainability objectives (Geng & Maimaituexun, 2022). The goal of green marketing is to create and market goods and services that both meet the needs of people and do so with little harm to the environment (Qureshi & Mehraj, 2022). Which improved the company's financial and non-financial performance (Visamitanan & Assarut, 2021). This study adopted green product, green price,

green distribution, green promotion and green branding as measures of green marketing from prior studies of Alabo and Anyasor, (2020); Nguyen, (2023).

Green products are designed to minimize negative environmental impact throughout their life cycle (Bhardwaj et al, 2023). Tsai et al (2020) defined green products as harmless products to use and are ecologically friendly. These are products characteristically created through ecologically more friendly procedures. Nguyen (2023) argued that the concept of green product is used generally to describe those products with ecologically friendly features of its materials, manufacturing processes, distribution processes, disposal and recycling procedures or product functionality (e.g. low energy consumption). Green products have created new opportunities in their market offerings and promoted businesses to become environmentally responsible (Mukonza & Swarts, 2020). Augustini et al (2021) maintain that green products should encompass the whole life cycle from design, material procurement, manufacture, storage, distribution, and usage to post-usage activities.

Green pricing refers to setting product prices based on environmental benefits. This may involve charging a premium for products that are environmentally friendly, energy-efficient, or sustainably produced (Gattupalli et al, 2025). Nguyen (2023) provides that green pricing practices accounts for both the economic and environmental costs of production and marketing while providing value for customers and a fair profit for business. Given the customer intentions to obtain reliable

information, including feather of product features, about environmental concerns (Nguyen, 2023), customers are willing to spend more money on environmentally friendly products and services (Tsai et al., 2020; Gelderman et al., 2021). Therefore, customers are prepared to pay a higher price for ecologically friendly products and services as they understand that their eco-friendly knowledge impacts their ecological behaviour (Gelderman et al., 2021). According to prior research, green price perceptions directly influence consumer satisfaction (Gelderman et al., 2021). Therefore, green price can create higher green satisfaction.

Green distribution (place) focuses on reducing environmental impacts throughout the supply chain and logistics (Alabo & Anyasor, 2020; Gattupalli et al, 2025). According to Nguyen (2023), green place is a complex set of decisions involving a network of activities that goes from material procurement to distribution channel management to the point of consumption. According to Davari and Strutton (2014), green place refers to management tactics related to distribution–thechainofproductiontoconsumption–andreverselogistics, reducing packaging (decreasing transportation costs, optimizing carriers and reducing material consumption), and using integrated transportation systems. Therefore, Green Place involves the selection of channels that ensure that there is minimal environmental damage (Mukonza and Swarts, 2020).

Green promotion involves communicating the environmental benefits of a product or firm

practices in an honest and transparent manner (Alabo & Anyasor, 2020; Gattupalli et al, 2025). Green promotion is described by Nguyen (2023) as an effective responsiveness instrument of communicating, informing and reminding stakeholders about their commitment and achievements toward environmental preservation efforts (Mukonza & Swarts, 2020). In general, green promotion refers to activities that educate and change consumers' views on green products and is expected to communicate substantive environmental information that contains meaningful relations to the company's activities (Agustini et al., 2021).

Green branding involves developing a brand identity that consistently reflects environmental values, building trust through eco-consciousness (Alabo & Anyasor, 2020; Gattupalli et al, 2025). Green branding refers to the process of developing and promoting a brand based on its environmentally sustainable values, products, and practices. It involves communicating a firm's commitment to environmentally responsibility such as reduced emissions, recyclable packaging, ethical sourcing, or low impact production to appeal to environmentally conscious consumers. It is more than a marketing tool; it assists in building a brand identity aligned with sustainability, increases customer trust, differentiates the brand from competitors, and can enhance long-term loyalty when supported by genuine ecological performance.

Concept of Customer Loyalty: Marketing researchers have explained diverse conceptualizations of customer loyalty. Different definitions of customer loyalty have

begun to be accepted by marketing researchers based on the research context's objectives and subject. Loyalty is the propensity for customers to return to a store or brand and make more purchases or referrals, whether they are purchasing the same thing or something completely different each time, and advocate for the same organization (Shariffuddin et al., 2023). The success of a business greatly depends on the loyalty of its customers. Customers are more likely to return and do repeat business when they are pleased with their most recent transaction (Puspitasari et al., 2023). Researchers have found that when customers are pleased with the services they receive, they are more likely to remain loyal to the company, laying the groundwork for future financial success (Chou et al., 2023). It is generally acknowledged that customer pleasure influences consumer behaviour, which in turn influences customer loyalty, but no academic framework has been developed to define these elements. There is a positive correlation between customer loyalty and service quality, suggesting that satisfied customers are more likely to remain loyal (Agarwal & Dhingra, 2023). This study used customer repurchase intention as a measure of customer loyalty. This is a predictive measure of customer loyalty, often used by marketers to evaluate the effectiveness of product offerings, brand strategy, and customer relationships management. In the context of green marketing, repurchase intention is particularly vital because environmentally conscious consumers are more likely to repeatedly buy products that align with their ethical and ecological values. It

is also defined as the consumer's willingness or likelihood to purchase a product or service again based on their prior experience. It is considered a major indicator of customer loyalty, satisfaction, and long-term business sustainability (Bhardwaj et al, 2023). It is commonly understood as a post purchase behavioural intention, reflecting the customer's predisposition toward repeated purchasing rather than a one-time transaction. Because its connection previous consumption outcomes to future purchase behaviour, repurchase intention is often used as a proxy indicator of customer loyalty (Wijarnoko et al, 2023; Feng et al, 2024).

Theoretical Review

This study is grounded on the customer value theory advanced by Woodruff (1997), Zeithami (1988), Slater and Narver (1994) that posits that customers make purchasing decisions based on the perceived value a product or service provides. This perceived value is a combination of functional, emotional, and social benefits relative to the costs incurred. The higher the perceived value, the stronger the likelihood of purchase, repeat purchase, and brand loyalty. Green marketing emphasises eco-friendly products, sustainability, and environmental responsibility. CVT can be applied to understand how green marketing practices influence customer perceptions and loyalty. Green products should offer high performance or durability comparable to conventional alternatives. In green marketing, CVT is used to understand how consumers weigh ecological benefits against traditional value dimensions such as price, quality, convenience, and brand

trust. CVT emphasizes that value is subjective and multidimensional, commonly comprising functional, emotional, social, and sometimes epistemic or conditional value (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001). In green marketing contexts, these value dimensions extend to include ecological benefits perceived by consumers (Nguyen et al, 2020). When consumers believe that a green product delivers superior functional performance, aligns with their emotions or identity, or contributes to the environment, their perceived value increases, enhancing their likelihood of adopting sustainable products. Additionally, CVT suggests that consumer behaviour is strongly affected by overall perceived value, making it a key predictor of purchase intention and brand preference. Consequently, in green marketing practice, CVT provides a robust foundation for explaining why consumers may choose ecologically friendly products despite potential price premiums or performance doubts. Applying CVT in green marketing practices as precursors of perceived customer loyalty. Therefore, green marketing practices positively affects perceived customer value. Perceived customer value positively impacts customer loyalty. Perceived value moderates the link between green marketing and customer loyalty. This application aligns with findings that customers are willing to remain loyal to brands that provide both functional and ecological benefits, highlighting the strategic relevance of integrating sustainability into marketing creativities (Rahman et al, 2020).

Empirical Review

Empirical investigations into the relationship between green marketing practices and customer loyalty have expanded considerably in recent years as sustainability has become a strategic concern within the hospitality industry. Existing studies generally suggest that green marketing practices positively influence customer loyalty through mediating variables such as customer satisfaction, trust, perceived value, brand engagement, and revisit intention. However, the strength and nature of these relationships vary across contexts, thereby necessitating further investigation, particularly within developing economies and environmentally sensitive regions such as the Niger Delta.

Chang et al (2024) investigated the impact of eco-friendly hotel practices on customer loyalty in Bangladesh. The study employed quantitative cross-sectional survey of hotel customers using partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) and fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis. The study found that green practices significantly enhance customer loyalty through customer satisfaction and environmental commitment. Customers who perceived hotels as genuinely environmentally responsible demonstrated stronger loyalty. The study provides empirical evidence that green operational practices directly influence customer loyalty and supports stakeholder and signaling theory. Jamwal et al (2024) analysed sustainability marketing and green customer behaviour in brand loyalty formation. The study employed quantitative empirical research design using structured questionnaires and respondents were customers of sustainable

brands while primary data collected was analysed using structural equation modeling. The findings revealed that sustainability marketing practices positively influenced green consumer behaviour, which subsequently enhanced brand loyalty. Consumer trust emerged as a significant mediator in the link. Their study demonstrates the mediating role of consumer trust between green marketing practices and customer loyalty. Mohammadi et al (2023) investigated the effect of green marketing strategy dimensions on brand loyalty. The study used survey research design with a population of employees and managers of food-exporting companies and a sample size of 182 respondents selected through random sampling and data was analysed using structural equation modeling (SEM). The findings indicated that green products, green promotion, green pricing, and green distribution all had significantly positive effects on brand loyalty. Green promotion exhibited the strongest influence. The study supports the multi-dimensional nature of green marketing practices and their impact on loyalty outcomes. Yuniasih et al (2024) conducted a study of how green marketing strategies influence brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers. The study used qualitative phenomenological research design and data collected using in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The participants were consumers with strong environmental awareness. The findings suggest that eco-friendly packaging, sustainability communication, and environmental initiatives positively influenced customer loyalty by improving emotional attachment and brand

trust. The study provides qualitative evidence supporting the link between green marketing initiatives and customer loyalty. Zhang et al (2023) conducted a comprehensive review of green loyalty research. The study employed bibliometric and content analysis as research design using web of science with a sample of 236 articles published between 2002 and 2022. The findings showed that green marketing, environmental responsibility, green satisfaction, green trust, and green perceived value were identified as the basic antecedents of customer loyalty. The review concluded that customer loyalty is a key outcome of successful green marketing initiatives. Oladipo et al (2025) examined the impact of green marketing initiatives on consumer decisions and brand loyalty using consumers of Nestle Nigeria products. The study used cross-sectional survey research design with a sample size of 900 consumers across Nigeria. Data was collected using structured questionnaires while data collected were analysing using ordinary least square and descriptive statistics. The study found that although consumers were aware of Nestle Nigeria's green marketing initiatives, awareness, credibility, and perceived effectiveness did not significantly influence brand loyalty. The authors attributed this outcome to consumer skepticism regarding environmental claims and recommended more authentic and measurable sustainability communication. The study demonstrates that green marketing alone may not guarantee customer loyalty unless consumers perceive the environmental claims as credible. Oranusi (2025) investigated the influence of eco-labeling

on brand loyalty among environmentally conscious consumers in Awka, Anambra State. The study employed correlational research design using a sample size of 400 consumers using purposive sampling with data collected using structured questionnaire. The data collected were analysed using simple regression. The findings revealed that eco-labeling significantly influenced brand loyalty. Consumers who perceived environmental labels as credible and informative showed stronger loyalty intentions and repeat purchase behaviour. The study provides evidence that green product communication can directly enhance customer loyalty. Braimah and Omoluabi (2023) examined the effect of green marketing on consumer purchasing behaviour in Nigeria. The study employed survey research design, and the variables are green branding, eco-labeling, environmental awareness, consumer purchasing behaviour and data was analysed using inferential statistical techniques. The findings indicated that green branding, eco-labeling, and environmental awareness significantly influenced consumer purchasing behaviour. Although loyalty was not directly measured, the findings suggest that positive green perceptions may improve long-term customer commitment. The study provides foundational evidence linking green marketing practices to positive consumer responses that may translate into loyalty. Usman et al (2025) investigated the influence of green marketing strategies on sustainable purchasing behaviour among FMCG consumers in North-East, Nigeria. The study employed survey research design with FMCG as the primary respondents

and structured questionnaire was used for data collection while multiple regression was used as the data analysis technique. The findings indicated that green marketing strategies significantly influenced sustainable purchasing behaviour. Consumers who perceived stronger environmental commitment from firms were more likely to exhibit repeat purchasing tendencies. The study provides evidence from FMCG on the effectiveness of green marketing strategies in shaping consumer behaviour. Asagba and Humprey (2025) examined the relationship between green product marketing and consumer buying behaviour of brewery products in South-South, Nigeria. The study employed cross-sectional survey research design with a sample of 400 consumers using stratified sampling. The data collected via questionnaire were analysed using regression analysis. The findings suggest that green product marketing significantly influenced consumers' buying behaviour. The study concluded that environmental product attributes positively affect consumer preferences and long-term patronage.

Methodology

This study adopted a positive research philosophy. This philosophy is appropriate because the study seeks to test hypothesised link between measurable constructs (green marketing practices and consumer loyalty) using quantitative data and statistical analysis. Also, the study adopted deductive approach, whereby hypotheses were developed from existing theories and empirical literature and subsequently tested using data collected from hotel customers. A cross-sectional survey design

was employed. This design was appropriate because data are collected at one point in time and it allows examination of links among latent constructs. The study was conducted in Yenagoa, the capital of Bayelsa State. The city hosts numerous hotels, guest houses and hospitality establishments serving business travellers, tourists, government officials, and residents. The target population comprised customers of registered hotels operating within Yenagoa metropolis. Because the exact number of hotel customers is difficult to determine, the population is infinite. Hence, for an unknown population, the Cochran (1977) formula was used to derive the sample size of 384 customers. The study employed purposive sampling to select major hotels in Yenagoa that actively engage in environmental initiatives, and systematic random sampling was used to select hotels guests. This study employed structured questionnaire as the main source of collecting primary data from the respondents, and the structured questionnaire was titled "Green Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty Questionnaire" (GMAPCULOQ). The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first section of the questionnaire sought vital personal information from the respondents while the second section consists of questions on the study variables. These questions used 5 – point Likert-type scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) while the respondents were required to indicate by a tick against the option that best expressed their opinion on the link between the independent variable (green marketing practices) and dependent variable

(customer loyalty). This study used content and face validity, where the instrument was given to marketing scholars, hospitality management experts and sustainability researchers who read through and made necessary corrections. Face validity refers to the extent to which a measure or assessment appears to measure what it claims to measure (Appah, 2020). The second process that was used to validate the instrument was that the questionnaire was pre-tested and the responses from the respondents were used to improve on the items. According to Appah (2020), test – retest reliability is the coefficient of correlation between two sets of scores obtained independently from administration of the same test twice with suitable time interval to the same group of members under similar condition. Cronbach Alpha (α) was used to ascertain the reliability of the research instrument with a good degree of reliability at 0.72, 0.66, 0.68, 0.64, 0.78 and 0.74 respectively. The responses collected from the questionnaires administered to hotel guests were analysed using univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis. The multiple regression was guided by a linear model below:

$$CUL = \beta_0 + \beta_1GPR + \beta_2GPI + \beta_3GPO + \beta_4GDI + \beta_5GBR + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:

CUL = Customer Loyalty, GPR = Green Product, GPI = Green Price, GPO = Green Promotion, GDI = Green Distribution, and GBR = Green

Branding. $\beta_0 - \beta_5$ represent the regression coefficient, while ε represents the error term. According to Appah (2020), the interpretation of correlation (r) parameters is 0.8 – 1.0 = very strong relationship, 0.6 – 0.79 = strong relationship, 0.4 – 0.59 = moderate relationship, 0.2 – 0.39 = weak relationship; and 0.0 – 0.19 = very weak or no relationship. The study utilised a 5% level of significance; hence we conclude that the coefficient is significantly different from zero at the 5% level if the p-values are less than or equal to 0.05. If it is greater than 0.05 then we cannot reject the null hypothesis that the coefficient is zero at our 5% significance level.

Data Presentation

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Out of 212 participants, 69.81% were male and 30.19% were female. The majority (49.06%) were between the ages of 26 – 35%, while 16.51% were between 18 – 25 years. Regarding marital status, 64.62% were single and 30.19% married. Most respondents (50.94%) possessed a secondary school certificate or diplomas, while 30.66% and 18.40% had either a bachelor's degree or postgraduate qualification. Occupationally, students 15.09%, self-employed 30.66%, public sector employees 43.43% while private sector employees 19.82

Table 1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Demographic Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	148	69.81
	Female	64	30.19
Age	18 – 25 years	35	16.51
	26 – 35 years	104	49.06
	36 – 45 years	48	22.64
	46 years and above	25	11.79
Marital Status	Single	137	64.62
	Married	64	30.19
	Divorced/Separated	11	5.19
Educational Qualification	Secondary/Diploma	108	50.94
	Bachelor's degree	65	30.66
	Master's degree and above	39	18.40
Occupation	Student	32	15.09
	Self-employed	65	30.66
	Public sector employee	73	34.43
	Private Sector employee	42	19.82

Source: Field Survey (2026)

Questionnaire Distribution

A total of Three Hundred and Eighty-Four (384) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. Out of this number, Two Hundred and Twelve (212) representing 55.21% response rates were correctly filled and returned while One Hundred and Thirty-Five (135) copies representing 35.15% were not returned.

However, Thirty-Seven (37) representing 9.64% were returned but not correctly filled and therefore rejected. The implication is that the analysis of data will be based on Two Hundred and Twelve (212) representing 55.21% response rates that were returned and correctly filled.

Table 2: Questionnaire Distribution

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid Number returned and correctly filled	212	55.21	55.21	55.21
Number returned and not correctly filled	37	9.64	9.64	64.85
Number not returned	135	35.15	35.15	100.0
Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2026) Via SPSS Output

Data Analysis

In this part of the study, data analysis has been done on the various variables and presented in tables respectively. Using the modified Likert

scale, the keys to the tables are as KEY: SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, UD= Undecided, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Green Product

S/ N	Items	N	Min	Ma x	Mean	Std. D
1	This hotel provides environmentally friendly products and amenities for guests.	212	1.00	5.00	3.254	1.243
2	The products used in this hotel (e.g., toiletries, package, and cleaning product) are environmentally sustainable)	212	1.00	5.00	3.216	1.258
3	The hotel uses reusable, recyclable, or biodegradable products whenever possible.	212	1.00	5.00	3.271	1.265
4	The green products provided by this hotel meet my quality experiences.	212	1.00	5.00	2.948	1.251
5	The hotel's use of green products demonstrates a genuine commitment to environmental protection.	212	1.00	5.00	2.842	1.283
Valid N (listwise)		212			3.106	1.260

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in table 3 show the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on green product of green marketing variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled, and the mean

and standard deviation of the five items were calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on green product of green marketing. Notwithstanding, all the items mean are above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items

disclosed (**Mean =3.642; Std. D =1.260**) respectively.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Green Price

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	The prices of this hotel’s environmentally friendly products and service are reasonable	212	1.00	5.00	2.743	1.254
2	I believe the products and services offered by this hotel provide good value for the price charged.	212	1.00	5.00	2.846	1.252
3	I am willing to pay a slightly higher price for this hotel’s environmentally friendly products and services	212	1.00	5.00	3.214	1.231
4	The additional cost of this hotel’s green products and services is justified by their environmental benefits	212	1.00	5.00	2.873	1.253
5	The pricing of this hotel’s green products and services is fair compared to similar hotels.	212	1.00	5.00	2.725	1.225
Valid N (listwise)		212			2.880	1.243

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in table 4 reveal the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on green price of green marketing variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were

calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on green price of green marketing. Notwithstanding, all the items mean are above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean = 2.880; Std. D =1.243**) respectively.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Green Promotion

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	This hotel effectively communicates its environmental initiatives and practices to	212	1.00	5.00	2.863	1.353

	guests					
2	The hotel's promotional messages clearly emphasise its commitment to environmental sustainability	212	1.00	5.00	2.872	1.242
3	The hotel provides adequate information about the environmental benefits of its products and services	212	1.00	5.00	3.365	1.248
4	The hotel's environmental advertisements and promotions are credible and trustworthy	212	1.00	5.00	2.914	1.214
5	The hotel's green promotional activities increase my awareness of its environmentally friendly practices.	212	1.00	5.00	3.523	1.236
Valid N (listwise)		212			3.107	1.259

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in table 5 show the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on green promotion of green marketing variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled, and the mean and standard deviation of the five

items were calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on green promotion of green marketing. Notwithstanding, all the items mean are above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.107; Std. D =1.259**) respectively.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics of Green Distribution

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	This hotel sources its products and supplies through environmentally responsible channels.	212	1.00	5.00	3.452	1.313
2	The hotel makes efforts to reduce environmental impacts associated with the delivery and distribution of tis products and services	212	1.00	5.00	3.163	1.241
3	The hotel priorities locally sourced products to minimise transportation related environmental impact	212	1.00	5.00	3.316	1.242

4	The hotel's distribution and supply practices reflect a commitment to environmental sustainability	212	1.00	5.00	2.874	1.235
5	The hotel ensures that products are delivered and made available to guests in an environmentally friendly manner.	212	1.00	5.00	2.962	1.242
Valid N (listwise)		212			3.153	1.255

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in table 6 present the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on green distribution of green marketing variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled, and the mean and standard deviation of the five

items were calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on green distribution of green marketing. Notwithstanding, all the items mean are above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =3.153; Std. D =1.255**) respectively.

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics of Green Branding

S/N	Items	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D
1	This hotel has established a strong reputation for environmental responsibility	212	1.00	5.00	2.984	1.237
2	I perceive this hotel as an environmentally friendly brand	212	1.00	5.00	2.847	1.248
3	The hotel's brand reflects a genuine commitment to environmental sustainability	212	1.00	5.00	2.875	1.252
4	The hotel's environmental values positively influence my perception of its brand	212	1.00	5.00	2.683	1.325
5	The hotel's green image distinguish it from competing hotels.	212	1.00	5.00	2.718	1.317
Valid N (listwise)		212			2.821	1.276

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in table 7 reveal the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on green branding of green marketing variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were calculated to determine the overall mean and

standard deviation responses on green branding of green marketing. Notwithstanding, all the items mean are above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean =2.821; Std. D =1.276**) respectively.

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of Customer Repurchase Intention

S/ N	Items	N	Min	Ma x	Mean	Std. D
1	I intend to revisit this hotel in the future	212	1.00	5.00	2.748	1.314
2	I am likely to use this hotel again when I need similar services	212	1.00	5.00	2.684	1.253
3	This hotel would be my first choice among other hotels	212	1.00	5.00	3.521	1.261
4	I will continue to patronise this hotel in the future	212	1.00	5.00	3.265	1.272
5	I would choose this hotel even if other hotels offer similar services	212	1.00	5.00	3.254	1.284
Valid N (listwise)		212			3.094	1.277

Source: Field Survey (2026)

The results in table 8 reveal the descriptive statistics of the mean and standard deviation responses on customer repurchase intentions variable using five questionnaire items that were designed on a five-point Likert scale. Thus, the questionnaire items labelled, and the mean and standard deviation of the five items were

calculated to determine the overall mean and standard deviation responses on customer repurchase intentions. Notwithstanding, all the items mean are above the cut-off point of 2.5. However, the grand mean and standard deviation responses on the questionnaire items disclosed (**Mean = 3.094; Std. D =1.277**) respectively.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Analysis

Table 9: Results of Correlation Matrix

	CUL	GPR	GPI	GPO	GDI	GBR
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CUL Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	Pearson	1 .000 212					
GPR Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	Pearson	.628** .000 212	1 .000 212				
GPI Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	Pearson	.664** .000 212	.624** .000 212	1 .000 212			
GPO Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	Pearson	.684** .000 212	.642** .000 212	.626** .000 212	1 .000 212		
GDI Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	Pearson	.684** .000 212	.624** .000 212	.648** .000 212	.642** .000 212	1 .000 212	
GBR Correlation Significant (2 tailed) N	Pearson	.628** .000 212	.646** .000 212	.624** .000 212	.682** .000 212	.626** .000 212	1 .000 212

Source: Authors' Computation Via SPSS (2026)

The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) analysis shows the relationship between green marketing practices

and customer repurchase intentions of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Table 9 shows a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.628$, $P = 0.00$) between green products (GPR) and customer repurchase intentions (CUL) of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria; a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.664$, $P = 0.000$) between green price (GPI) and customer repurchase intentions (CUL) of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria; a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.684$, $P = 0.000$) between green promotion (GPO) and customer repurchase intentions (CUL) of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria; a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.684$, $P =$

0.000) between green distribution (GDI) and customer repurchase intentions (CUL) of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria; and a strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.628$, $P = 0.000$) between green branding (GBR) and customer repurchase intentions (CUL) of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The findings therefore suggested a strong and positive relationship between green marketing practices (green product, green price, green promotion, green distribution and green branding) and customer repurchase intentions of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Table 10: Multiple Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: CUL

Method: Least Squares

Date: 06/18/26 Time: 19:12

Sample(adjusted): 1 212

Included observations: 212 after adjusting endpoints

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.275444	2.256856	1.451330	0.1488
GPR	0.285935	0.095662	2.989017	0.0256
GPI	0.249495	0.106627	2.339885	0.0342
GPO	0.216547	0.102573	2.111150	0.0404
GDI	0.273341	0.123184	2.218965	0.0384
GBR	0.234756	0.112637	2.126453	0.0326
R-squared	0.682826	Mean dependent var		12.99346
Adjusted R-squared	0.528439	S.D. dependent var		3.098167
S.E. of regression	2.888766	Akaike info criterion		4.997962
Sum squared resid	1226.711	Schwarz criterion		5.116803
Log likelihood	-376.3441	F-statistic		5.567008
Durbin-Watson stat	2.16401	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000100

Source: e-view output (2026)

Table 10 reveals the multiple regression analysis of the relationship between green marketing practices and customer repurchase intentions of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The finding revealed a positive and statistically significant ($0.0256 < 0.05$) relationship green product (GPR) and customer repurchase intentions (CUL) of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant ($0.0342 < 0.05$) relationship between green price (GPI) and customer repurchase intentions (CUL) of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant ($0.0401 < 0.05$) relationship between green promotion (GPO) and customer repurchase intentions (CUL) of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant ($0.0384 < 0.05$) relationship between green distribution (GDI) and customer repurchase intentions (CUL) of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A positive and statistically significant ($0.0326 < 0.05$) relationship between green branding (GBR) and customer repurchase intentions (CUL) of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Hence, there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between green marketing practices (green product, green price, green promotion, green distribution and green branding) and customer repurchase intentions of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The R^2 (coefficient of determination) of 0.682826 and adjusted R^2 of 0.5284393 show that the variables combined determine about 68% and 53% of green marketing practices (green product, green price, green promotion,

green distribution and green branding) and customer repurchase intentions of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The F-statistics and its probability show that the regression equation is well formulated, explaining that the relationship between the variables combined affects customer repurchase intentions of the hospitality sector in Bayelsa State, Nigeria is statistically significant (F-stat = 5.567008; F-prob. = 0.000100).

Discussions of Findings

Green Product and Customer Repurchase Intentions: The finding of this study reveal a positive and statistically significant relationship between green products and customer repurchase intention in the hospitality industry in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. This implies that guests who perceive hotel products and services as environmentally friendly are more likely to revisit and continue patronising such establishments in the future. This finding is consistent with existing empirical evidence in the hospitality literature which confirm that green practices and environmentally friendly products significantly influence customers' behavioural intentions, including revisit and repurchase intention. For example, studies have shown that green practices in hotels enhance perceived value and satisfaction, which subsequently increase customers' intention to return and recommend the hotel to others (Chen et al, 2026). Similarly, research grounded in environmental marketing theory demonstrates that green marketing elements such as green products positively affect loyalty-related outcomes including

repurchase intention and word-to-mouth behaviour. According to Seo et al (2024), hotel green marketing activities significantly influence behavioural intentions such as revisit intention and customer loyalty, particularly when customers perceive such initiatives as credible and valuable. Furthermore, findings from a Nigerian hospitality context also support this result. Studies on green practices in hotels reveal that environmentally responsible service delivery positively affects guest satisfaction and willingness to repurchase, both directly and indirectly through improved customer experience (Adeniran et al, 2026). This suggests that in developing nations such as Nigeria, environmental consciousness among hotel guests is increasing, and green product offerings are becoming an important determinant of repeat patronage. Therefore, the result implies that hotels in Yenagoa that adopt and visibly implement green product strategies are more likely to retain customers and encourage repeat patronage, thereby improving competitive advantage and long-term sustainability.

Green Price and Customer Repurchase Intentions: The hypothesis two result reveal a positive and statistically significant relationship between green price and customer repurchase intention in the hospitality industry in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. This implies that when hotel customers perceive that the pricing of environmentally friendly products and services is fair, reasonable, and offers good value, they are more likely to revisit and continue patronising the hotel in the future. This result concurs with the established hospitality and green marketing literature, which emphasise

that price fairness and perceived value are critical determinants of customer behavioural intentions, including loyalty and repurchase intention. This result is consistent with established hospitality and green marketing literature, which perceived value are critical determinants of customer behavioural intentions, including loyalty and repurchase intentions. Recent empirical studies confirm that customers are increasingly willing to pay a premium for green hotels, and this willingness is directly linked to their behavioural intentions, including revisit and repurchase intention (Wei et al, 2023). For instance, in the study conducted by Wei et al (2023) shows that consumers' willingness to pay a premium price for green hotels is significantly influenced by perceived environmental benefits and psychological value, which in turn improves loyalty and revisit intention. Studies in hospitality research indicate when customers perceive hotel pricing as fair relative to service quality and environmental benefits, they develop trust and emotional attachment, which significantly increases their intention to revisit (Lv et al, 2024; Shehawy et al, 2024)). Additionally, research on green hotel consumption behaviour demonstrates that green pricing influences repurchase intention indirectly through perceived value and satisfaction. Customers are more likely to revisit hotels when green pricing enhances their perceived environmental contribution and personal value (Damigos, 2023). This suggests that green price functions not only as an economic factor but also a psychological and ethical value indicator in hospitality

consumption. Generally, prior empirical evidence consistently supports that green price has a positive and statistically significant relationship between green price and customer repurchase intention in the hospitality industry. The link is primarily explained through perceived value, price fairness, guest satisfaction, and willingness to pay a premium for environmentally friendly services. Therefore, hotels that adopt fair and transparent green pricing strategies are more likely to achieve stronger customer loyalty and repeat patronage.

Green Promotion and Customer Repurchase Intentions: The hypothesis three result reveal a positive and statistically significant relationship between green promotion and customer repurchase intention in the hospitality industry in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. This finding suggests that customers are more likely to revisit and repurchase hospitality services when they perceive that hotels and other hospitality establishments actively communicate their environmental sustainability initiatives through promotional responsibility projects appear to strengthen customers' favourable attitudes toward hospitality establishments and encourage repeat patronage. The finding concurs with recent empirical evidence showing that green marketing significantly enhances repurchase intentions across service industries. Begendik and Karadeniz (2026) found that green marketing practices exert a direct positive effect on customers repurchase intentions, indicating that sustainability-oriented promotional strategies can influence customers' decisions to continue patronizing a service

provider. The authors argued that environmental marketing initiatives strengthen customers' perceptions of value and trust, thereby encouraging repeat purchases. Similarly, Huang et al (2024) found that green marketing practices positively influence repurchase intention and positive word-to-mouth through the mediating effects of trust and customer identification with environmentally responsible brands. Furthermore, the finding aligns with the study of Huyen et al (2025), who established that green practices contribute significantly to the development of green image and green trust, which subsequently increase customers' revisit intentions within the hospitality industry. Their findings suggest that customers are more likely to return to hospitality establishments that consistently communicate and demonstrate their commitment to environmental sustainability. The result is also in agreement with Dan-Van et al (2024), who found that green hotels practices significantly influence consumers' revisit intentions through enhanced brand identification and green consumption value. The authors argued that sustainability-oriented promotional messages create emotional and psychological connections between customers and hospitality brands, thereby encouraging repeat visitation. This suggests that customers in Yenagoa may perceive green promotional campaigns as indicators of responsible business conduct, which positively affects their repurchase decisions. The present study also agrees with Nangpiire et al (2024), who observed that sustainable hospitality practices positively affect

customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions. Their study emphasized sustainability initiatives create additional value for customers, thereby increasing the likelihood of repeat purchase. Green promotion therefore acts as a communication mechanism that informs customers about these sustainability efforts and reinforces positive perceptions of the hospitality brand.

Green Distribution and Customer Repurchase Intentions: The hypothesis four result reveal a positive and statistically significant relationship between green distribution and customer repurchase intention in the hospitality industry in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. This result suggests that customers are more likely to revisit and continue patronizing hospitality establishments that adopt environmentally friendly distribution practices. The result indicates that customers increasingly value environmental responsibility and incorporate such considerations into their future purchase decisions. The result is consistent with previous empirical studies. For instance, Nangpiire et al (2024) found that environmental sustainability dimensions within hospitality supply chains significantly influence customer repurchase intentions. Their study demonstrated that sustainable hospitality supply chain practices directly affect customers' decisions to continue patronizing hospitality services. Similarly, Adeniran et al (2026) reported that green practices in Nigerian hotels positively influence customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions, emphasizing that environmentally responsible operations encourage customers to maintain long-term

relationships with hospitality firms. Furthermore, the significant relationship suggests that green distribution may improve customers' overall service experience. Sustainable distribution practices often enhance operational efficiency, ensure timely service delivery, reduce waste, and demonstrate a firm's commitment to quality and responsibility. These benefits contribute to higher customer satisfaction levels, which subsequently increase the likelihood of repeat patronage. Existing literature indicates that customer satisfaction serves as an important mechanism through which sustainable practices influence customer loyalty and repurchase behaviour (Majeed et al, 2022; Karim et al, 2024). For hospitality managers in Yenagoa, this finding highlights the need to integrate green distribution into their operational strategies. Investments in eco-friendly transportation systems, sustainable procurement processes, recyclable packaging materials, and energy-efficient logistics can generate positive customer perceptions and strengthen repeat patronage. Therefore, the finding demonstrates that environmentally sustainable distribution practices are increasingly important determinants of customer loyalty in the hospitality industry.

Green Branding and Customer Repurchase Intentions: The hypothesis five result reveal a positive and statistically significant relationship between green branding and customer repurchase intention in the hospitality industry in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The result indicates that customers are more likely to revisit and continue patronizing hospitality establishments that project a strong

environmentally responsible brand image. The finding suggests that customers increasingly value environmental responsibility and are willing to reward businesses that demonstrate genuine commitment to sustainability through repeat patronage. The finding may be attributed to the ability of green branding to enhance customers' perceptions of a firm's environmental commitment. When hospitality organisations consistently communicate environmentally friendly values through their brand image, customers tend to develop favourable attitudes, trust and emotional attachment toward the brand. These positive perceptions subsequently increase their willingness to revisit and repurchase services. According to Huyen et al (2026), green image and green trust significantly enhance customers' green revisit intentions in the hospitality industry, indicating that environmentally responsible branding plays a critical role in influencing future customer behaviour. The result further suggests that green branding serves as a vital source of competitive advantage within the hospitality industry. Dang-Van et al (2024) found that green hotel practices positively influence revisit intentions through brand identification and perceived green consumption value, emphasizing the strategic relevance of environmental branding in the hospitality sector. Similarly, Khuong et al (2025) reported that green innovation practices significantly enhance guests' return intentions through the mediating effects of green hotel image, customer satisfaction, and positive emotions. Their findings indicate that customers who perceive a hotel as

environmentally responsible are more likely to develop favourable feelings toward the brand and subsequently exhibit stronger intentions to return. The finding is also consistent with recent studies showing that green brand image improves customers' behavioural intentions. Safer et al (2025) found that green image significantly influences customers' continuous stay intentions in sustainable hospitality settings by improving organisational credibility and environmental trust. Furthermore, Chen et al (2026) observed that green brand environments constitute an important component of the overall green servicecape that positively influences customer loyalty and revisit intentions. Therefore, the findings indicate that hospitality firms in Yenagoa can improve customer retention and loyalty by investing in green branding initiatives.

Conclusion, Policy Implications of the Study, Limitations and future Studies

The study concludes that green marketing mix dimensions of green product, green price, green promotion, green distribution, and green branding – each have a positive and statistically significant relationship with customer repurchase intentions in the hospitality industry in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The empirical evidence confirms that environmentally sustainable marketing practices are fundamental determinants of customer loyalty and repeat patronage in the hospitality sector. The result on green product indicates that environmentally friendly service offerings and sustainable operational outputs significantly enhance customers' willingness to revisit hospitality establishments. Similarly, the

finding on green price suggests that customers respond positively to fair and environmentally conscious pricing strategies, particularly when they perceive added environmental and ethical value in service delivery. Furthermore, the significant effect of green promotion demonstrates that effective communication of environmental initiatives improves customer awareness, trust, and emotional engagement, which in turn enhances repurchase intentions. The positive relationship between green distribution and repurchase intentions further confirms that eco-efficient logistics, reduced environmental impact in service delivery and sustainable supply chain practices contribute to favourable customer evaluations and long-term patronage behaviour. In addition, green branding emerged as a strong predictor of customer repurchase intentions, indicating that a well-established environmental brand identity enhances customer trust, perceived credibility, and emotional attachment to hospitality firms. Generally, the findings establish that green marketing practices function as an integrated strategic framework that significantly influences customer behavioural intentions in the hospitality sector. The study therefore concludes that hospitality organisations in Yenagoa that effectively integrate and communicate green marketing strategies are more likely to achieve higher customer retention, improved brand loyalty, and sustainable competitive advantage. The findings that green product, green price, green promotion, green distribution, and green branding all have a positive and statistically significant connection with customer

repurchase intentions in the hospitality industry in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria, carry important policy implications for government, industry regulators, and hospitality managers. First, the result on green product implies that policymakers should encourage the adoption of environmentally friendly products and services within the hospitality sector through standards, certification systems, and compliance frameworks. Regulatory bodies such as tourism boards and environmental agencies can develop clear guidelines for sustainable product offerings to ensure consistency across the industry. Second, the significance of green price suggests that governments and industry regulators should promote pricing policies that balance environmental sustainability with affordability and customer welfare. Policymakers can support firms through subsidies or tax incentives for adopting green technologies. Third, the finding on green promotion highlights the need for regulatory oversight of environmental communication in the hospitality sector. Policymakers should ensure that promotional claims linked to sustainability are accurate, transparent, and free from greenwashing. Fourth, the positive link between green distribution and repurchase intentions suggests that infrastructure and logistics polices should support sustainable operations in the hospitality industry. Government investment in green infrastructure would enable hospitality firms to adopt more sustainable distribution practices. Policies should encourage collaboration between logistics providers and hospitality firms can further enhance environmental efficiency across

the supply chain. Finally, the significance of green branding indicates that policymakers should promote national or regional sustainability branding initiatives within the tourism and hospitality sector. Generally, the findings imply that an integrated policy framework combining regulation, incentives, infrastructure development, and public awareness is basic for improving green marketing practices in the hospitality industry. Despite the valuable contributions of this study, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study was geographically limited to the hospitality sector in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. As a result, the findings may not be fully generalizable to other regions in Nigeria or to different cultural and economic contexts where customer perceptions of green marketing practices may differ. Second, the study focused on five dimensions of green marketing (green product, green price, green promotion, green distribution and green branding) without incorporating other potentially relevant variables such as green trust, green satisfaction, etc. The exclusion of these mediating or moderating variables may limit a more comprehensive understanding of how green marketing influences customer repurchase intentions. Third, the study relied on cross-sectional data, which captures respondents' perceptions at a single point in time. This design limits the ability to establish causal links between green marketing practices and customer repurchase intentions. Longitudinal studies would provide stronger evidence of causality and allow for the observation of changes in customer behaviour over time.

Fourth, the study used self-reported data from customers, which may be subject to response bias, including social desirability bias and common method bias. Respondents may overstate their pro-environmental attitudes or repurchase intentions, thereby affecting the accuracy of the results. Fifth, the study focused primarily on customer perceptions without incorporating the perspectives of hospitality managers of internal organisational factors that may influence the successful implementation of green marketing strategies.

Future research should expand the geographical scope of the study to include other states in Nigeria and different regions across Africa to enhance the generalizability of the findings. Comparative studies between urban and rural hospitality markets could also provide deeper understandings into contextual differences in green marketing effectiveness. Further studies should incorporate additional variables such as green trust, green satisfaction, perceived value, environmental awareness, and corporate social responsibility to develop a more comprehensive model of customer repurchase intention in the hospitality industry. Researchers may also explore mediating and moderating effects to better explain the mechanisms through which green marketing influences customer behaviour. In addition, future research should consider longitudinal research designs to investigate changes in customer perceptions and behaviour over time, particularly as environmental awareness continues to evolve. Experimental or mixed-method approaches could also be employed to improve causal inferences and enrich the qualitative findings with quantitative

understanding. Moreover, future studies could include the perspectives of hotel managers, employees, and policymakers to provide a more holistic understanding of the implementation and effectiveness of green marketing strategies.

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